

A systematic review on the potential of agro-industrial waste for pyrolysis: feedstocks properties and their impact on biochar and pyrolysis gas composition

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ABSTRACT

Massive agro-industrial waste is generated yearly due to tree pruning, food processing, and crop residues. Pyrolysis can convert agro-industrial waste into valuable products such as biochar, bio-oil, and pyrolysis gas. However, there is a lack of systematic reviews that comprehensively evaluate the potential of various agro-industrial wastes for pyrolysis to produce energy and biochar. In this study, the Scopus database was used to gather literature. The statistical analysis was performed on a defined set of agro-industrial wastes (tree pruning, nutshells, crop residues, and pomace waste) to identify significant differences in properties and suitability for pyrolysis. In general, the investigated feedstocks were characterised by high higher heating value (16–21 MJ/kg), which followed the trend: pomace > pruning > nutshells > crop residues. The higher heating value (HHV) of the resulting pyrolysis gas was in the range of 5–16 MJ/Nm³, which shows its potential for sustainable energy production. Correlation analysis revealed that elevated temperatures support pyrolysis gas production and the HHV of pyrolysis gas due to increased H₂ and C_nH_m concentrations. Pruning and nutshell biochar properties, such as surface area, showed their potential for pollutant adsorption. The high cation exchange capacity and nutrient contents depicted pomace and crop-residue biochar suitability for soil amendment. The preferred feedstocks for a pyrolysis plant aiming to produce good-quality biochar and pyrolysis gas are pruning > nutshells > pomace > crop residue. This literature review provides insights on a solution for agri-food sector operators and farmers to valorise agro-industrial waste locally to produce energy and biochar.

Nomenclature

AC	Ash content
B_ash	Biochar ash content
B_C	Biochar carbon content
B_FC	Biochar fixed carbon content
B_N	Biochar nitrogen content
B_S	Biochar sulphur content
B_VM	Biochar volatile matter content
CEC	Cation exchange capacity
CR	Crop residue
EC	Electrical conductivity
FC	Fixed carbon
MC	Moisture content
OT	Operating temperature
PW	Pomace waste

(continued on next column)

(continued)

SA	Surface area
SHP	Shells, hulls, and pits
VM	Volatile matter
WB	Woody biomass

1. Introduction

Agro-industrial waste refers to the residues produced during post-harvest, pruning, and food preparation. Agro-industrial waste generation has risen substantially in previous decades due to rapid population growth [1,2]. Typically, the agro-industrial waste contains pomaces, nutshells, crop residues, and tree pruning. Some wastes can be managed

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as by-products (e.g., used in animal feed processing), but most are still treated and disposed of as waste [2,3]. The improper waste management of agro-industrial waste can cause greenhouse gas emissions into the environment, such as methane (CH_4), which strongly contributes to climate change [1,4]. There are some technologies that can produce energy and value-added products from agro-industrial waste. For instance, anaerobic digestion can process wet waste and produce biogas and digestate; biogas can produce energy, while digestate can be used in soil amendment. However, anaerobic digestion is suitable for easily degradable biomass such as food waste and manure rather than ligno-cellulosic biomass such as pruning, shells and hulls, etc [5]. Moreover, incineration plants are primarily used in waste management because they rapidly reduce waste volume and produce heat for electricity production [6]. Although incineration has high energy output potential, it generates air pollutants that harm the environment and human health [7,8]. Therefore, incorporating the proper air-pollution control devices is essential to make the incineration plants environmentally sustainable. On the other hand, gasification is an attractive technology that produces syngas with higher energy content from agro-industrial waste. Still, it operates at higher temperatures and demands stringent feedstock preparation [9,10]. Thus, regarding resources, environment, and sustainability, pyrolysis can convert agro-industrial waste into biochar, pyrolysis gas, and bio-oil while reducing environmental impact [11,12]. Moreover, pyrolysis offers feedstock flexibility and typically operates at lower temperatures. The energy production potential of pyrolysis gas is lower than that of syngas [13]. Some hybrid approaches, such as pyro-gasification, can be used when the focus is to produce pyrolysis gas for energy applications [9,14]. However, pyro-gasification systems have higher capital and operational costs [13]. Fig. 1 depicts the possible conversion pathway of agro-industrial waste through the pyrolysis process. The pyrolysis process is often classified into slow, fast, and flash pyrolysis. Slow pyrolysis is ideal for biochar production due to prolonged residence time (>5 min), low heating rate (<1 °C/s), and low operating temperature (300–700 °C) [15]. Whereas fast pyrolysis is suitable for high bio-oil production due to high temperature (450–800 °C), high heating rate (>50 °C/s), and short residence time (0.5–10 s). In contrast, flash pyrolysis is preferred for producing pyrolysis gas since it happens at a higher temperature (1000–1200 °C), a higher heating rate (1000 °C/s), and a shorter residence period (<2 s) [15,16].

Bio-oil is a dark brown liquid obtained by condensing the vapours and gases in the condenser. It is a complex mixture of acids, ketones, phenols, hydrocarbons, aldehydes, and water [17]. Separating and extracting a specific compound from bio-oil is challenging and expensive [18]. The presence of organic compounds depicts bio-oil utilisation as a fuel source for furnaces or boilers to produce energy. However, the complex composition including water and oxygenated compounds limit its direct utilisation as a fuel source [18,19]. On the other hand, pyrolysis gas is a mixture of various non-condensable gases, and its energy potential relies on the fraction of combustible gases such as carbon monoxide (CO), hydrogen (H_2), CH_4 , and hydrocarbons (C_nH_m) [20,21]. While biochar produced from agro-industrial waste can be used in

various applications such as soil amendment [22], wastewater treatment [23], thermo-composting [24], etc., depending on its properties. Although the bio-oil from pyrolysis of agro-industrial waste is recognised as a valuable product, this study primarily focused on investigating biochar and pyrolysis gas to valorise agro-industrial waste on farms to produce energy and biochar. While for bio-oil produced from agro-industrial waste, it is believed that a separate comprehensive study should be conducted to evaluate bio-oil properties and upgrading techniques to use on farms or extract value-added products.

Several studies investigated the properties of individual agro-industrial waste to analyse their potential for pyrolysis gas or biochar production [25–27]. The proximate, ultimate, biochemical characterisations (i.e., hemicellulose, lignin, cellulose) and higher heating value (HHV) are widely used to evaluate the feedstocks' potential for the pyrolysis process [28]. Moreover, the HHV of pyrolysis gas, determined by its composition (i.e., CO, CH_4 , CO_2 , H_2 , C_nH_m) and process parameters, helps to assess its potential for energy production [20,25]. Likewise, biochar properties such as carbon and nitrogen content, ash, pH, surface area (SA), cation exchange capacity (CEC), electrical conductivity (EC), and H/C and O/C ratios are key indicators to foresee its potential application (e.g., as adsorption media, soil amendment, etc.) [11,29]. Moreover, seasonal availability makes relying on specific agro-industrial waste throughout the year challenging. The harvesting season of some feedstocks differs from others, likely causing availability problems when relying on particular feedstocks. Some agro-industrial wastes have diverse physio-chemical properties directly impacting their heating value [30]. Consequently, it is recommended that each feedstock's capability for pyrolysis be evaluated to guarantee uninterrupted operation by maintaining product quality and feedstock supply. In this context, a systematic comparison between the different agro-industrial wastes in terms of their suitability as feedstocks for pyrolysis and the resulting pyrolysis gas and biochar utilisation is needed.

Addressing this gap, this study reviews the scientific literature comprehensively, analysing the potential of a defined set of agro-industrial waste for pyrolysis, by focusing on the following objectives:

- 1 Compare agro-industrial waste proximate, ultimate and biochemical properties, HHV, and lower heating value (LHV).
- 2 Compare and analyse pyrolysis gas yield, composition (CO, CH_4 , CO_2 , H_2 , C_nH_m), HHV, and LHV generated from the pyrolysis of the investigated set of agro-industrial waste.
- 3 Compare the agro-industrial waste-derived biochar yield and properties, such as pH, SA, EC, CEC, and nutrient content, to assess biochar potential end-use applications.

In particular, the set of agro-industrial feedstocks investigated in this study includes, among others, tree pruning (grapes, almond, olive, peach, apricot), almond hulls and shells, grape pomace, and crop residues (wheat straw, corn stalk, cotton stalk) to answer one of the research objectives of the TEAPOTS project (a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Union) [31]. The TEAPOTS project aims to provide a solution for agri-food sector operators and farmers to valorise agro-industrial waste locally to produce energy and biochar.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data collection and review strategy

A comprehensive literature search was performed in the Scopus database. The search strings used in the Scopus database to identify the relevant articles are presented in the supplementary material (file named SM-1), specifically in Table S1. The search strings were developed separately for feedstock properties, pyrolysis gas, and biochar analysis. No year limit was applied for the articles search; the search includes the articles up to January 2025. Fig. S1 illustrates the selection and screening process of articles for feedstock, pyrolysis gas, and biochar

Fig. 1. Pyrolysis of agro-industrial waste for biochar and energy production.

analysis. Initially, the studies were selected based on their title, abstracts, and keywords. In full-text screening, the inclusion criteria were based on articles that reported the experimental data of agro-industrial waste properties (proximate, ultimate, biochemical, HHV and LHV), pyrolysis gas (yield, composition, HHV, and LHV), and biochar (proximate, ultimate, SA, pH, EC, CEC, and nutrient content). The articles that did not focus on agro-industrial waste were excluded. Additionally, review articles and simulation-based studies were not considered in the analysis. Only the peer-reviewed journal articles were included in the datasets to minimise the bias. The detailed review methodology, including data extraction strategy from articles and statistical analysis, is illustrated in Fig. S2.

The final datasets were based on 242 articles for feedstock analysis, 55 articles (171 experimental results) for pyrolysis gas analysis, and 77 articles (274 experimental results) for biochar analysis. Fig. S1 illustrates the details of the article search and screening. Moreover, the dataset built from each article is available in the supplementary material (file named SM-2).

The data collected from the literature exhibits high heterogeneity due to different measurement techniques, process parameters, feedstock characteristics, etc. To reduce this heterogeneity during data collection, the data was collected on the dry basis of feedstock and standardised into the same measurement units to perform analysis. Data standardisation details are explicitly described in Section 2.2. Furthermore, to manage the heterogeneity and to facilitate comparison of results, data from specific agro-industrial residues were grouped into four feedstocks groups based on the origin and structural characteristics: woody biomass (WB), crop residues (CR), pomace waste (PW), and shells, hulls, and pits (SHP), as outlined in Table 1. The feedstocks' grouping helps reduce the group's internal variation and makes the data more comparable. The visualisation of data was presented through box-whisker plots. Nonetheless, some outliers and variability within groups indicate that heterogeneity still exists in the data, which may be due to inherent differences in biomass source [32]. The difference in geographic origin, agronomic practice, post-harvest processing, etc. can significantly influence the properties of the same biomass type [33]. Additionally, for pyrolysis gas and biochar analysis, the datasets were stratified into two temperature ranges (200–450 °C and 451–1000 °C), further increasing the data homogeneity and enabling the clear interpretation of results.

2.2. Data standardisation and statistical analysis

The collected data were analysed in OriginPro 2025 (V 10.2.0.188). Statistically significant differences in the means of specific parameters were determined between groups by ANOVA using the Tukey test (0.05 significance level).

Missing values or calculation units were standardised before statistically analysing the data. When missing in the literature studies, the oxygen content present in the feedstocks and the LHV of feedstocks were calculated from Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) [34], respectively.

$$O(\%) = 100 - (C + H + N + S + \text{ash}) \quad (1)$$

Table 1

Grouping of specific agro-industrial feedstocks considered in the scope of this study.

Group	Feedstocks
Woody biomass (WB)	Tree pruning of olive, grapes, peach, apple, plum, almond, apricot, cherry, citrus, mango, etc.
Crop residues (CR)	Wheat straw, corn cob, corn stalk, cotton stalk, rice stalk, rice husk, grapes stalk, rape stalk, sugarcane bagasse etc.
Pomace waste (PW)	Olive pomace, grape pomace, orange pomace, raspberry pomace, etc.
Shells, hulls, and pits (SHP)	Almond shells and hulls, olive pits, hazelnut shells, coconut shells, walnut shells, etc.

$$\text{LHV (MJ/kg)}_{\text{feedstock}} = \text{HHV (MJ/kg)} - 0.2122 \cdot H - 0.0008 \cdot (O + N) \quad (2)$$

Where O is oxygen percentage, C is carbon, H is hydrogen, N is nitrogen, and S is sulphur in percentage.

When not reported in the literature, the LHV of pyrolysis gas was calculated from Eq. (3) [35–37], while the HHV of pyrolysis gas was calculated from Eq. (4) [38].

$$\text{LHV (MJ/Nm}^3\text{)}_{\text{gas}} = (30 \cdot \text{CO} + 25.7 \cdot \text{H}_2 + 85.4 \cdot \text{CH}_4 + 151.3 \cdot \text{C}_n\text{H}_m) \cdot 0.0042 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{HHV (MJ/Nm}^3\text{)}_{\text{gas}} = (12.79 \cdot \text{H}_2 + 12.64 \cdot \text{CO} + 39.82 \cdot \text{CH}_4 + 70.30 \cdot \text{C}_n\text{H}_m) \quad (4)$$

Where CO , H_2 , CH_4 , and C_nH_m are the percentages of carbon monoxide, hydrogen, methane, and hydrocarbons in the pyrolysis gas, respectively.

The values calculated from equations are highlighted in green in the supplementary material (file named SM-2).

If the LHV or HHV of pyrolysis gas was presented in MJ/kg, it was converted into MJ/Nm³ to standardise the units by assuming the density of pyrolysis gas to be 1.2 kg/Nm³ [39].

2.3. Modelling and prediction of HHV for feedstocks and pyrolysis gas

The HHV of a feedstock is critical in determining its potential use as a suitable feedstock for pyrolysis. Typically, a bomb calorimeter is used to measure the HHV of feedstocks. However, the bomb calorimeter is expensive, and HHV analysis is time-consuming. Therefore, the prediction of HHV of feedstocks based on ultimate and proximate analysis has importance [40]. Minitab (V 21.4.1) was used to model a predictive equation for the HHV of feedstocks and pyrolysis gas. Pearson correlation analysis was performed to determine the influential independent variables affecting feedstocks' HHV and pyrolysis gas. The stepwise backwards elimination method ($\alpha = 0.1$) was used during the regression modelling, which eliminates some of the independent variables based on p-value (>0.05). Furthermore, the outliers from the dataset were removed using Minitab regression diagnostics tools, which improved the model's data homogeneity and predictive performance. The regression models were tested for p-values for statistical significance (<0.05) and R^2 values for goodness of fit (0.9–1).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Suitability of agro-industrial feedstocks for pyrolysis

3.1.1. Proximate analysis

Fig. 2 illustrates the proximate analysis results, highlighting significant property differences between the investigated feedstocks groups. The data collected for proximate analysis of agro-industrial waste shows that each feedstock group can be considered suitable for pyrolysis, depending on the targeted product (e.g., biochar, bio-oil, or pyrolysis gas).

The mean moisture content (MC) in feedstocks was less than 15 %, indicating that the dataset's feedstocks could have been dried before the experiment to reach values in the range (5–20 %), as recommended in the literature [41]. However, some studies also reported that the initial MC in woody biomass (WB) was 35–45 % [42], and in pomace waste (PW) was 60–80 % [43,44]. The CR and SHP groups contained less initial moisture (<20 %), which shows their suitability for pyrolysis in terms of less energy consumption during the drying process [45]. Additionally, if the feedstock is not well-dried, the HHV of the feedstock and the quality of pyrolysis products will be affected. Ash content (AC) is crucial in evaluating feedstocks' potential for pyrolysis. CR contained a significantly higher amount of AC, followed by PW, SHP, and WB. The

Fig. 2. Results of proximate analysis of agro-industrial feedstocks (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, \blacksquare represents the interquartile range (25%–75%), \square represents the mean, $-$ represents the median, and \blacklozenge represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

ashes from biomass contain alkali and alkaline earth metals, which can promote or inhibit the decomposition of biomass during pyrolysis [46]. However, the higher AC in feedstocks limits its exploitation for pyrolysis because ash accumulates in biochar, which can limit biochar utilisation in soil amendment and adsorption applications [47]. The high AC in CR can decrease the efficiency of the pyrolysis reactor due to slagging and fouling, which can cause poor heat transfer and blockage of gas pathways [48]. Therefore, the appropriate way to deal with high AC biomass could be the pretreatment or co-pyrolysis with another feedstock that contains less AC.

The mean volatile matter (VM) contents in agro-industrial wastes are high (>65%), as shown in Fig. 2. The VM was highest in WB, followed by CR, PW, and SHP. The high VM can be linked with a significant presence of hemicellulose and cellulose content in the feedstocks, which decompose at low temperatures. In pyrolysis, the VM represents the organic fraction of biomass emitted as condensable and non-condensable gases during heating. The feedstocks with high VM are suitable for producing bio-oil and pyrolysis gas through fast or flash pyrolysis [45]. The PW contained more fixed carbon (FC) contents than SHP, WB, and CR, indicating that it can produce C-rich biochar during pyrolysis. The high FC content in agro-industrial waste is also associated with the high lignin content, which decomposes slowly in a wide temperature range during pyrolysis and results in a higher biochar yield [49].

3.1.2. Ultimate analysis

Fig. 3 demonstrates the data collected regarding the ultimate analysis of agro-industrial waste feedstocks. The C content in the feedstocks groups was significantly different. The C content was considerably higher in PW, followed by SHP, WB, and CR. The mean value of C content was greater than 45% among all feedstock groups. C content is present in the form of lignin, hemicellulose, and cellulose in the agro-industrial waste [50]. The C content is crucial in determining the energy potential of feedstock as it directly influences the heating value. The mean value of H content was about 6%, among all feedstock groups.

Fig. 3. Results of ultimate analysis of agro-industrial feedstocks (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residues, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, \blacksquare represents the interquartile range (25%–75%), \square represents the mean, $-$ represents the median, and \blacklozenge represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

The H content was significantly higher in PW than in WB, SHP, and CR. H content is bounded with O and C in agro-industrial waste, and when the agro-industrial waste is heated in an inert atmosphere, the H bond breaks and produces water (H_2O), H_2 , CH_4 , and other hydrocarbons (C_nH_m) [51]. The feedstocks with high H content are suitable for producing pyrolysis gas with high HHV due to the foreseen high content of H_2 and C_nH_m [52]. Fig. 3 depicts that the PW contains high N content, followed by CR, WB, and SHP. However, no significant difference exists in the mean value of N content for CR, SHP, and WB. In agro-industrial waste, the N content originates from proteins, which can be the reason for the high N content present in PW. The S content is very low in agro-industrial waste (<1%). However, regarding the comparison of feedstocks, the highest S content was found in CR, while the other feedstocks have relatively low S content. Moreover, high S and N content in feedstocks causes emission of air pollutants during pyrolysis, such as SO_x , NO_x , hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), and hydrogen cyanide (HCN), which can cause potential environmental risk [53]. The mean value for O content was similar and high for CR, WB, and SHP (>40%). In contrast, the O content in PW was relatively low, as shown in Fig. 3. The high O content in agro-industrial waste is due to the abundance of carbonyl (C=O) and hydroxyl (O-H) functional groups. Furthermore, O-containing functional groups in the feedstocks generate more CO and carbon dioxide (CO_2) during pyrolysis [54,55].

3.1.3. Biochemical analysis

Fig. 4 represents the biochemical analysis of the investigated agro-industrial wastes, which shows significant differences in hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin contents. Typically, agro-industrial waste contains 85–90% of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin, while the rest consists of inorganic minerals and organic extractives [56]. Hemicellulose is primarily found in CR, followed by SHP, WB, and PW. Hemicellulose is a branched polysaccharide with high reactivity and low molecular weight; therefore, it decomposes at lower temperatures during pyrolysis. Moreover, the high hemicellulose content in feedstocks results in low HHV of feedstocks [57]. The mean value of cellulose

Fig. 4. Results of biochemical analysis of agro-industrial feedstocks (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, \blacksquare represents the interquartile range (25 %–75 %), \square represents the mean, $-$ represents the median, and \blacklozenge represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

content in agro-industrial wastes is approximately similar, except PW, showing lower values. Cellulose is a crystalline polymer consisting of monomeric units of glucose, which decompose at relatively higher temperatures than hemicellulose [56]. The lignin content was high in PW, followed by SHP, WB, and CR, as shown in Fig. 4. Lignin is a complex phenolic macromolecule with an aromatic structure that slowly decomposes in a broader range of temperatures than cellulose and hemicellulose [49,57]. The higher lignin content in PW reflects the high FC and C content, as previously shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Moreover, high lignin-containing feedstocks result in high HHV compared to cellulose and hemicellulose [57]. From a pyrolysis perspective, feedstocks with high lignin content are preferable for producing biochar through slow pyrolysis [49]. The mean value of feedstocks extractives is statistically similar, which may be due to the small sample size. The extractives in agro-industrial waste are non-structural components containing proteins, lipids, inorganic minerals, etc. The extractives were primarily found in PW and CR, possibly due to the presence of protein (N content was also high, as in Fig. 3) or inorganic minerals, respectively.

3.1.4. HHV and LHV of feedstock

Fig. 5 illustrates the HHV and lower heating value (LHV) of the analysed groups of agro-industrial waste. The HHV and LHV are used to evaluate the potential energy recovery of feedstocks through pyrolysis. Literature frequently reported the heating value in two terms, HHV and LHV. Therefore, both heating values were considered in this literature review. The LHV is defined as the amount of heat available in agro-industrial waste, excluding the latent heat of vaporization of water in the reaction products and agro-industrial wastes. At the same time, the HHV includes the latent heat of vaporization of water [45]. The HHV and LHV show a similar trend, except in SHP. The HHV and LHV were high in PW, likely due to higher FC, C, and lignin content. Moreover, the mean value of HHV of WB and SHP was higher than CR. This is likely due to high hemicellulose, AC, and CR's low C and FC content [58], as shown in previous proximate, ultimate, and biochemical analyses (Figs. 2–4). Therefore, the PW, WB, and SHP were suitable for producing energy-dense pyrolysis products. At the same time, the CR can be

Fig. 5. Results of HHV and LHV analysis of agro-industrial feedstocks for pyrolysis potential (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, \blacksquare represents the interquartile range (25 %–75 %), \square represents the mean, $-$ represents the median, and \blacklozenge represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

pretreated or co-pyrolysed to compensate for their poor properties as energy carriers [59].

3.1.5. Prediction of HHV based on agro-industrial feedstocks properties

The Pearson correlation analysis, followed by regression analysis, was performed on parameters of proximate and ultimate analyses to predict the HHV of agro-industrial waste. In the literature, proximate and ultimate analysis are widely used in predicting the HHV of biomass, compared to biochemical analysis. This could be because proximate and ultimate analyses are relatively simple and quick. The Pearson correlation analysis was conducted on each agro-industrial waste group to identify their composition's impact on HHV, as shown in Fig. S3. The correlation coefficient between the parameters of proximate and ultimate analysis with HHV showed a similar pattern among the groups, with the exception of some parameters for PW, likely due to the presence of high extractives, which can affect the HHV differently compared to other groups. Therefore, it was decided to perform a Pearson correlation analysis followed by a regression analysis on the whole dataset to see the independent variables with strong positive and negative correlation coefficients with HHV and to model the predictive equation. Fig. 6 shows the correlation of feedstocks properties with HHV, which indicates that the HHV of feedstocks was influenced by C, FC, VM, O, H, and AC of feedstocks. The C and FC depict a positive correlation coefficient with HHV, while the VM and H showed a moderate positive correlation. Moreover, the AC, MC, and O content negatively correlated with HHV. The Pearson correlation analysis provides evidence of findings from previous proximate, ultimate, and HHV analyses that the HHV of feedstocks increases with high FC and C levels and decreases with higher AC, O, and MC levels.

The regression equations were separately modelled based on proximate and ultimate analysis. Table 2 shows the HHV predictive equations based on proximate and ultimate analysis. Eq. (5), obtained based on ultimate analysis, showed high prediction accuracy ($R^2 = 0.92$), while Eq. (6), based on proximate analysis, showed low prediction accuracy ($R^2 = 0.57$). The literature also presents that the accuracy of HHV prediction based on ultimate analysis ($R^2 = 0.79$, Eq. (7)) was higher than that of proximate analysis ($R^2 = 0.61$, Eq. (8)) because the parameters of

Fig. 6. Pearson correlation between feedstocks properties and HHV of feedstocks (whole dataset). In the heatmap, white colour represents the neutral correlation, dark red colour depicts the strong positive correlations, and dark blue colour shows strong negative correlations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 2

Equations of models obtained from regression analysis to predict HHV based on proximate and ultimate analysis.

No.	Equation	R ²	Ref.
Eq. (5)	HHV = - 2.01 + 0.4505C + 0.3391H - 0.0602O	0.92	This study
Eq. (6)	HHV = 9.78 - 0.110MC + 0.085VM + 0.181FC - 0.132AC	0.57	This study
Eq. (7)	HHV = 0.005 + 0.38C + 1.065H - 0.1061O	0.79	[66]
Eq. (8)	HHV = - 3.0368 + 0.2218VM + 0.2601FC	0.61	[67]

Notes: C is carbon content (%); H is hydrogen content (%); O is oxygen content (%); MC is moisture content (%); VM is volatile matter (%); FC is fixed carbon (%); and AC is ash content (%).

ultimate analysis provide more information on the chemical composition of biomass [60]. The higher the R² value (0.9–1.0), the better the prediction accuracy of the model [61]. For Eq. (5), the R² value was more significant than 0.90, and the residuals were randomly scattered around the zero line, which shows its accuracy in predicting the HHV of agro-industrial wastes. The higher R² of the predictive model based on ultimate analysis indicates the high prediction reliability because the elemental composition (C, H, and O) is directly related to the chemical energy of agro-industrial feedstock [62]. Hence, the model provides a fast estimation of the HHV of various agro-industrial wastes based on ultimate analysis without performing more bomb calorimetric experiments. On the other hand, the model based on proximate indicates reduced accuracy in HHV prediction because it does not fully capture the elemental details influencing the energy content of feedstock [60, 62]. The model based on proximate analysis may offer rapid estimation of the HHV of agro-industrial waste for low-resource settings. Still, their use for policy assessment or energy system design should be cautiously approached. Adopting advanced modelling techniques such as artificial neural networks (ANNs) and combining ultimate and proximate

analyses provides more accurate predictions of HHV of agro-industrial waste than using either analysis alone [63]. Pattanayak et al. [64] utilised the multi-layer perceptron artificial neural network (MLP-ANN) to predict the HHV of bamboo biomass based on proximate, ultimate, and combined (proximate-ultimate) parameters. Their findings show that the combined model has superior prediction accuracy (R² = 0.999) than the proximal (R² = 0.985) and ultimate models (R² = 0.968). Joshua et al. [65] utilised MLP-ANN to predict the HHV of biomass based on combined proximate and ultimate parameters. The results show that the HHV prediction accuracy of the model was high (R² = 0.9249).

3.2. Characterisation of pyrolysis gas from agro-industrial feedstocks

3.2.1. Pyrolysis gas yield and composition

Pyrolysis gas is produced during the pyrolysis of agro-industrial waste, which can generate heat and electricity depending on the HHV of pyrolysis gas [55]. The yield and composition of pyrolysis gas are influenced by operating temperature (OT) and the properties of agro-industrial waste [21,68]. Therefore, selecting and screening agro-industrial feedstocks and optimising process parameters are vital to achieving the energy production objective of pyrolysis gas. The yield of pyrolysis gas can be calculated from Eq. (9).

$$\text{Pyrolysis gas (\%)} = 100 - (\text{Biochar (\%)} + \text{Oil (\%)})) \quad (9)$$

The identified studies discussed the yield and composition of pyrolysis gas derived from a heterogeneous set of operating process parameters. In this context, it was considered that OT mainly influences the pyrolysis gas yield and composition. Therefore, two OT ranges were used to distinguish the effect of temperature on the yield and composition of pyrolysis gas: 200–450 °C and 451–1000 °C. The yield of pyrolysis gas varied across both temperature ranges and agro-industrial waste groups, as shown in Fig. S4. Typically, at 200–450 °C, pyrolysis gas contains condensable vapours (bio-oil and water) that separate from pyrolysis gas in the condensation process and favours the higher yield of liquid products than pyrolysis gas. At 200–450 °C, the yield of pyrolysis gas from SHP, PW, and WB was higher than CR, possibly due to less cellulose content in CR. The yield of pyrolysis gas increased with the increase in cellulose content in the agro-industrial waste [68]. However, the yield of pyrolysis gas is not directly correlated with the individual effect of lignin, hemicellulose, and cellulose, but the combined effect of these three components can be considerable [69]. At 451–1000 °C, no significant difference was observed in the yield of pyrolysis gas among the feedstock's groups. The yield of pyrolysis gas increased at higher temperatures, including CR, due to enhanced thermal cracking and secondary reactions that break down bio-oil and biochar into pyrolysis gas [12,68].

Although the effect of feedstock properties and OT on pyrolysis gas is discussed in detail, the other factors also influence the yield and composition of pyrolysis gas, such as heating rate, residence time and reactor design [70]. These are crucial factors in optimising the pyrolysis process, but this study did not statistically analyse these variables due to inconsistent reporting in the literature. The higher heating rates promote the yield of pyrolysis gas due to the rapid decomposition of agro-industrial waste, which limits the secondary biochar formation [71]. The longer vapour residence time in the reactor also promotes the yield of pyrolysis gas due to the cracking of bio-oil [12]. Moreover, pyrolysis reactors with efficient heat distribution can promote the secondary reaction, which significantly increases the yield of pyrolysis gas, such as fluidised bed and entrained flow reactors [72]. While the fixed bed and Auger reactor inhibit the secondary reaction due to a poor heat transfer mechanism and moderate process parameters, which produce a low to medium yield of pyrolysis gas [73]. Hyungseok et al. [74] performed pyrolysis of rice husk on three different reactors: fluidised bed, batch, and bench-scale auger reactors. They found that the yield of pyrolysis gas was higher in the fluidised bed reactor (23 %), followed by the auger (13.2 %) and the batch reactor (11.5 %). Alexander et al. [75]

utilised the fluidised bed and batch reactor to perform the pyrolysis of pinewood and found that the fluidised bed reactor produces more yield of pyrolysis gas (30 %) than the batch reactor (18 %) due to the formation of secondary reactions.

The HHV of pyrolysis gas can be calculated based on its composition to determine its potential for energy applications. Fig. 7 shows the pyrolysis gas composition from various agro-industrial feedstocks at different temperature ranges. Pyrolysis gas yield and composition for each feedstock group showed high variability across both temperature ranges, determining an overall non-significance of the calculated means among the groups. This is due to the inherent heterogeneity of biomass composition, selection of temperature ranges for analysis, and small sample size (n) within certain feedstocks groups (PW and SHP) in the lower temperature range, which can introduce uncertainty. In these cases, caution is required when interpreting trends for agro-industrial feedstock groups.

The concentration of CO₂ and CO in pyrolysis gas was dominant in all feedstock groups in both temperature ranges. The hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin content present in the feedstocks influence the composition of pyrolysis gas [54]. Hemicellulose decomposition occurs at 200–315 °C, cellulose at 315–400 °C, and lignin at 160–900 °C during pyrolysis [76]. The feedstocks with more cellulose and lignin content produce more CO, CH₄, and C_nH_m, while those with high AC and hemicellulose content produce more CO₂ [54,77]. During the pyrolysis, at 200–450 °C, the high concentration of CO and CO₂ is associated with the decomposition of carboxyl and carbonyl functional groups. At the same time, the CH₄ and C_nH_m are due to the decomposition of methoxy groups [78,79]. Moreover, the feedstocks with high O content produce more C-O compounds (CO₂ and CO) [55]. The H₂ yield at 200–450 °C across all feedstock groups was not significant, and it increased with secondary reactions such as decompositions of aromatic functional groups, which take place at 451–1000 °C [79], as shown in Fig. 7. Thus, the H₂ concentration in pyrolysis gas increased as the condensation and dehydrogenation reactions occurred at higher temperatures [55]. Moreover, the concentration of H₂ in the pyrolysis gas is also associated with the H content in the parent feedstocks and the lignin content [54]. The increase in temperature clearly shows that the concentration of CO₂ decreases due to secondary reactions that convert CO₂ into CO [76], and increase the concentration of H₂, CH₄, CO, and C_nH_m. In summary, higher temperatures produce pyrolysis gas with a higher fraction of combustible gases that can be used in energy production.

Fig. 7. Effect of different feedstock types and operating temperatures on pyrolysis gas composition (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, ■ represents the interquartile range (25 %–75 %), □ represents the mean, – represents the median, and ◆ represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

3.2.2. HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas

The HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas are essential indicators for pyrolysis gas utilisation in energy production. Fig. 8 illustrates the HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas for agro-industrial wastes at various temperature ranges. The type of agro-industrial waste and temperature influence the HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas. In the literature, there was inconsistency in presenting HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas; therefore, both values were recorded for separate analysis. At 200–450 °C, the variability in HHV and LHV was low compared to 451–1000 °C. This is due to increased HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas at higher temperatures. The HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas primarily depend on the composition of pyrolysis gas, which indeed depends on the properties of agro-industrial waste and OT, as previously explained (Section 3.2.1). At 200–450 °C, the HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas were mainly dependent on the concentration of CO, as it is the only combustible gas with a high fraction in pyrolysis gas at this temperature range. However, at 451–1000 °C, CH₄, H₂, and C_nH_m also contribute to the pyrolysis gas's LHV and HHV. The LHV and HHV of pyrolysis gas were higher in WB in both temperature ranges as compared to other feedstocks groups, which is due to a balanced portion of cellulose and lignin content, which promotes CO, CH₄, and H₂ concentration in pyrolysis gas [80]. Typically, the HHV of pyrolysis gas obtained from lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose is 21.5 MJ/Nm³, 14.2 MJ/Nm³, and 11.1 MJ/Nm³ [81]. Therefore, the feedstocks that contain high lignin and cellulose content compared to hemicellulose content have high HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas. At 451–1000 °C, HHV and LHV of pyrolysis gas were higher, likely because of the decrease in CO₂ concentration and increase in the concentration of combustible gases [78], as shown in Fig. 8.

The HHV of pyrolysis gas from various agro-industrial waste was 12–18 MJ/Nm³ (median value) at higher temperatures, which is comparatively lower than natural gas (34.40 MJ/Nm³). The high HHV of natural gas is due to the presence of high CH₄ and a trace amount of CO₂ and C_nH_m, while the pyrolysis gas mainly contains high CO₂ concentration and a comparatively low amount of CH₄ and C_nH_m [21]. However, the HHV of pyrolysis gas can be increased by capturing CO₂ and increasing the concentration of H₂ with the introduction of catalysts [17, 80]. Various sorbents, such as alkali metal-based, CaO-based, amine-based, etc., are used to capture CO₂ from pyrolysis gas, which increases the HHV of pyrolysis gas by increasing H₂ and reducing CO₂ [26].

Fig. 8. Higher heating value (HHV) and lower heating value (LHV) of pyrolysis gas during pyrolysis of various feedstocks at different operating temperatures (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits). In the box-whisker plot, ■ represents the interquartile range (25 %–75 %), □ represents the median, – represents the mean, and ◆ represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

3.2.3. Modelling and prediction of HHV of pyrolysis gas

The Pearson correlation analysis was performed in two temperature ranges (200–450 °C and 451–1000 °C) to see the effect of feedstocks' properties, operating temperature (OT), and composition of pyrolysis gas on the HHV of pyrolysis gas. The Pearson correlation analysis was performed on individual feedstocks groups in both temperature ranges, as presented in Figs. S5–S8. However, the correlation coefficient between some properties of feedstocks (C, H, and FC) and the HHV of pyrolysis gas did not reflect the trend presented in the published literature when analysing the WB and PW feedstock groups. Therefore, the Pearson correlation analysis was performed on the whole dataset to see the effect of feedstocks properties and process parameters on pyrolysis gas composition and HHV, as shown in Fig. 9. At 200–450 °C, the impact of feedstocks properties on HHV of pyrolysis gas was pronounced, showing that C, FC, H have positive correlation coefficient with HHV of pyrolysis gas, as shown in Fig. 9a. At 451–1000 °C, the effect of feedstocks properties was not prominent, shown in Fig. 9b. Moreover, Fig. 9c depicts that the OT and pyrolysis gas composition positively correlated with the HHV of pyrolysis gas, except CO₂. This indicates that the HHV of pyrolysis gas mainly depends on the OT and composition of pyrolysis gas at higher temperature instead of feedstocks properties, as shown in Fig. 9d. Moreover, the correlation analysis validated the previous results that a high fraction of combustible gases in the pyrolysis gas increases the HHV of pyrolysis gas at elevated temperatures (Figs. 7 and 8). At the same time, CO₂ negatively impacted the HHV of pyrolysis gas, limiting its energy application.

Regression analysis was performed to model the equation that can

predict the HHV of pyrolysis gas using the backwards elimination method ($\alpha = 0.1$). The properties of feedstocks that show positive and negative correlation coefficients were chosen along with the OT to model equations in both temperature ranges (200–450 °C and 451–1000 °C). The R² values for equations of models at 200–450 °C and 451–1000 °C were 0.56 and 0.42, respectively, after the elimination of the independent variable having high p-values ($p > 0.05$), as presented in Table S2. The low R² value in both temperature ranges (0.56 and 0.42) reflects the inherent complexity of pyrolysis gas formation, which depends on factors such as OT, heating rate, feedstock composition, residence time, etc [70]. Moreover, the developed regression models could not capture them all together precisely, as these factors may interact non-linearly. The regression models are simple and capable of describing the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, but their simplicity can be their drawback for data following a non-linear relationship [82]. The developed models to predict the HHV of pyrolysis gas can provide initial insights, but the low accuracy limits their use in detailed design or optimisation without further refinement. The literature lacks a prediction of the HHV of pyrolysis gas based on feedstock properties and process parameters, which shows the potential research gap. However, the prediction accuracy of HHV of pyrolysis gas based on feedstock composition and process parameters can be improved using data-driven and non-linear approaches such as support vector machines (SVMs), ANNs, or hybrid ensemble models. These approaches can increase the predictive performance by capturing complex non-linear relationships. Simon et al. [82] compared various models to predict the yield and properties of pyrolysis products. Their findings

Fig. 9. Pearson correlation chart between (a) feedstocks properties and HHV of pyrolysis gas at 200–450 °C (b) feedstocks properties and HHV of pyrolysis gas at 451–1000 °C (c) operating temperature (OT), pyrolysis gas composition and HHV at 200–450 °C (d) OT, pyrolysis gas composition and HHV at 451–1000 °C. (HHV (FS): HHV of feedstock, HHV (gas): HHV of pyrolysis gas). In the heatmap, white colour represents the neutral correlation, dark red colour depicts the strong positive correlations, and dark blue colour shows strong negative correlations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

depict that the machine learning (ML) approaches have great potential for predicting product yield and properties. Xing et al. [83] developed ANNs and SVMs models to predict the pyrolysis products distribution and HHV of bio-oil. The R^2 value obtained from ANNs model (0.831–0.932) is lower than SVMs model (0.895–0.938) which shows the SVMs model performed well in predicting the HHV of bio-oil and pyrolysis products yield (biochar, bio-oil, and pyrolysis gas). Moreover, integrating simulation-based tools can provide deeper insights into the pyrolysis process of agro-industrial waste. For instance, Daniela et al. [84] performed the combined simulation using Cape-Open to Cape-Open (COCO) to predict the yield of pyrolysis products and SimaPro to conduct life cycle assessment to see the environmental impact. Their findings depict that the COCO simulation's predictive performance agreed with experimental product yield. At the same time, the environmental impact can be reduced in earlier stages of the process by employing renewable energy sources and electricity-saving measures. Thus, ML techniques and combined simulation analysis can be more accurate in predicting the HHV of pyrolysis gas. These approaches indicate a promising direction for future research to optimise the production of pyrolysis gas for energy applications.

3.3. Biochar yield and properties

3.3.1. Biochar yield

Biochar is a C-rich product obtained from the pyrolysis of agro-industrial wastes, and it can be used in several applications according to its characteristics. The type of agro-industrial feedstocks and OT significantly influences the yield and properties of biochar [85]. Typically, the yield of biochar is calculated from Eq. (10).

$$\text{Biochar yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Mass of biochar (wt)}}{\text{Mass of feedstock (wt)}} \times 100 \quad (10)$$

Consistent with the analysis done for pyrolysis gas, two ranges were chosen to evaluate the effect of OT and feedstock compositions on biochar yield and properties (200–450 °C for low temperatures and 451–1000 °C for high temperatures). The yield of biochar decreased with the increase in OT, as shown in Fig. S9. The average biochar yield for agro-industrial waste groups at lower OT range was higher ($45 \pm 14\%$) than that of biochar yield at the higher OT range ($29 \pm 4\%$). This can be due to the release of more volatiles and the secondary reaction (char-volatiles) occurring at higher temperature ranges, which reduces the biochar yield and increases the bio-oil and pyrolysis gas yield [68,85]. At 200–450 °C, no significant difference in the mean value of biochar yield was observed between feedstock groups. Typically, the agro-industrial waste that contains high lignin and FC content (as in PW) results in a higher biochar yield than that with more hemicellulose and cellulose content [49]. However, at 451–1000 °C, a significantly higher biochar yield was noted in CR (31%), which is due to ash accumulation in the biochar that increases the yield of biochar as compared to lignin-rich feedstocks [33], as shown in Fig. 2, CR had high AC.

Apart from the influence of feedstock properties and OT on biochar yield and properties, heating rate, residence time, and reactor design also influence the yield of biochar and its properties [70]. The slow heating rate and longer feedstock residence time in the reactor are usually preferred to produce biochar, as gradual decomposition occurs, which promotes carbon retention in the biochar [86]. Slow heating rates inhibit the formation of secondary reactions, resulting in a higher yield of biochar [87]. Fixed bed and auger reactors are well-suited for biochar production due to their ability to slow the heat transfer rate to biomass [73]. In contrast, a fluidised bed reactor produces less biochar and produces more volatiles due to the configuration of the reactor [74]. Higher heating rates and shorter residence times in the fluidised bed reactor promote secondary reactions and decrease biochar yield. However, to properly understand the effect of the pyrolysis reactor on product distribution, it is imperative to perform a pyrolysis experiment on different reactor designs under similar process parameter conditions.

Some studies can be found in the literature that performed pyrolysis on different reactors [72,74,75].

3.3.2. Biochar properties and possible end-use applications

3.3.2.1. Proximate and ultimate analysis. Investigating biochar's physicochemical properties is essential in determining biochar's application and optimising the process parameters. Fig. 10a shows the proximate analysis of biochar, and Fig. 10b illustrates the ultimate analysis. On average among groups, the biochar carbon (B_C), fixed carbon (B_FC), and ash (B_ash) increased with OT, while the biochar volatile matter (B_VM) was reduced compared to the parent feedstocks. At 451–1000 °C, high B_FC and B_C content represent the removal of carbonyl and hydroxyl functional groups, resulting in C-rich biochar [88]. No effect of temperature was observed on biochar sulphur (B_S) and nitrogen (B_N) content. A significant mean difference was observed in B_N and B_S content between the feedstock's groups in both temperature ranges. The high B_N content was found in the biochar obtained from PW and WB, which is due to the presence of more N-containing compounds like amino acids and chlorophyll [33]. High B_N content can support the further use of biochar as an N-fertiliser [89]. The B_S content was prominent in CR biochar in both temperature ranges, possibly due to the high S content in the parent CR (shown in Fig. 3), which was retained in biochar during pyrolysis. Recent studies show that high B_S can be used in various applications, such as electrodes in Li-S batteries and removing pollutants [90]. However, the B_N and B_S median contents in all feedstock groups were less than 3% and 1% (w/w). The

Fig. 10. Properties of biochar produced from various feedstocks groups at different temperature ranges (a) proximate analysis (b) ultimate analysis. (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells, hulls, and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, ■ represents the interquartile range (25%–75%), □ represents the median, and ◆ represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

B_{ash} was highest in CR, followed by PW, WB, and SHP in both temperature ranges. The high B_{ash} can limit the utilisation of biochar in soil amendment and adsorption applications by limiting the available sorption sites [91]. The mean value of B_{VM} was less than 40 % in all feedstock groups at 200–450 °C, which further reduced to less than 20 % at 451–1000 °C, as shown in Fig. 10a. The B_{VM} content at higher temperatures was decreased due to the release of hemicellulose and cellulose content. However, the high B_{VM} biochar is suitable for plant growth in soils with high N and low C, as it enhances microbial degradation and improves soil fertility [91]. Contrarily, biochar that contains high B_{VM} negatively impacts plant growth in N-deficient soil because it can reduce N availability due to microbial immobilisation [92]. At both temperature ranges, the B_{FC} and B_C contents were significantly higher in SHP, PW, and WB compared to CR, which could be due to high FC and lignin content in parent WB, PW, and SHP [31], as shown in Figs. 2 and 4. Typically, the B_C is divided into recalcitrant and labile C. Labile C is beneficial in enhancing soil microorganisms, while recalcitrant C shows higher resistance to microbial degradation and remains in the soil for a longer time [86]. Therefore, the production of biochar, which has recalcitrant C, can be considered as a C sequestration technique to reduce global warming and C emissions by storing C in such a way that it will not be released into the atmosphere [86]. The Van Krevelan diagram was plotted between the H/C and O/C ratios for parent feedstocks

and their resulting biochar to assess their C sequestration potential, as shown in Fig. S10. The H/C and O/C of biochar were less than those of the parent feedstocks due to the more aromatic structure of biochar. Biochar with an O/C ratio of 0.2 is considered very stable, characterised by an estimated half-life of 1000 years, thus showing high C sequestration potential [47]. The average O/C ratio of WB biochar was less than 0.2 at higher temperatures, showing its high C sequestration application potential, followed by PW, SHP, and CR biochar. The lower O/C ratio of CR indicates O-containing functional groups and hydrophilic surfaces [93]. Biochar having a H/C ratio of <0.4 indicates the presence of about 70 % of C and has a stability of about 100 years [94]. The H/C ratio was lowest in SHP biochar compared to other feedstocks groups, which shows the presence of carbohydrates and unsaturated carbons that are difficult for microorganisms to decompose. The average O/C and H/C ratio of all feedstock groups of biochar, except CR biochar, indicates high stability, which could be suitable for long-term C sequestration. Some biochar field studies depict that biochar sequestration in the soil improves the fertility of the soil, for example, Siwei et al. [95] performed a 10-year field experiment of corncob biochar carbon sequestration in Shandong province of China. They found that the biochar significantly increases the soil organic carbon, soil inorganic carbon, and total carbon content, which improves soil fertility and carbon sequestration. In another study, Xinyu et al. [96] conducted an

Fig. 11. Chemical and physical properties of biochar from pyrolysis of different agro-industrial feedstocks at different operation temperature ranges (a) pH (b) surface area (SA) (c) cation exchange capacity (CEC) (d) electrical conductivity (EC). (WB: woody biomass, CR: crop residue, PW: pomace waste, SHP: shells and pits, n: sample size). In the box-whisker plot, ■ represents the interquartile range (25 %–75 %), □ represents the mean, – represents the median, and ◆ represents the outliers. The different alphabetic letters (a, b, c) above the box-whisker plot represent the difference in the mean value.

11-year experiment on cottonseed husk (30 %) and rice husk (70 %) biochar at Shangzhuang, China. They observed that in maize and wheat residue retention fields, the biochar not only sequesters the carbon but also enhances the native soil organic carbon by improving the microbial activities.

3.3.2.2. Chemical and physical characterisation. Investigation and understanding of biochar physicochemical properties help determine biochar quality for suitable applications. Fig. 11 demonstrates the pH, surface area (SA), cation exchange capacity (CEC), and electrical conductivity (EC) of biochar of various agro-industrial feedstocks at different OT ranges. Fig. 11a depicts the pH of biochar produced from different agro-industrial waste groups. The pH of biochar is a key parameter in evaluating biochar potential for soil amendment. At 200–450 °C, the biochar produced from all feedstock groups showed a broad range of pH values. The low pH biochar (acidic to neutral) is effective for specific crop growth [33]. The biochar produced at higher temperatures was alkaline (8–11) in all feedstock groups. The pH value among all feedstocks groups increases with the increase in OT due to the formation of inorganic alkalis and mineral carbonate linked with the mineral phase [58]. Biochar with an alkaline pH can be exploited to amend acidic soil by neutralising it and enhancing its microbial activity [97]. Raboin et al. [98] applied 10 to 50 t ha⁻¹ of eucalyptus biochar in the acidic soil in Madagascar and found a significant increase in common bean and maize yield due to enhancement in the microbial activity in the soil. Fig. 11b represents the SA of biochar produced at different temperature ranges. The average SA of biochar produced at the lower OT range was remarkably lower (<43 m²/g) than that of biochar derived at the higher OT range (>114 m²/g). The SA of biochar increased as the OT increased, which is due to the elimination of VM, which enhanced the pore formation [99]. Differences among the groups were not apparent. However, at 451–1000 °C, the mean SA of WB (117 m²/g) and SHP (151 m²/g) biochar were higher, even if not significant, compared to PW (92 m²/g) and CR biochar (97 m²/g). VM elimination causes pore formation and increases biochar's SA. However, parent PW and CR feedstocks contained less VM than WB and SHP (as shown in Fig. 2), which caused less pore formation during pyrolysis, resulting in low SA in CR and PW biochar. Also, higher inorganic content could have determined lower SA in CR [100,101]. The higher SA in WB biochar was associated with the decomposition of cellulose and lignin content at higher temperatures. The lignin content in PW was also high, but in this kind of feedstocks, the pores can be dead-ended, which causes lower SA [101]. The WB and SHP biochar produced at higher temperatures could be suitable for adsorption applications such as contaminant adsorption from wastewater [102]. Moreover, implementing biochar in the soil can significantly mitigate the uptake of pollutants by plants by absorbing heavy metals due to its porous structure. For instance, Bian et al. [103] conducted a 3-year long-term evaluation of wheat straw biochar at Jingtang village, China, to observe the uptake of lead and cadmium in rice plants. They found that the uptake of lead and cadmium was reduced by 69 % and 67 %, respectively. Jiang et al. [104] applied the litchi branch biochar in a mining-contaminated soil in south China to reduce the lead and cadmium content. The results showed that the lead and cadmium uptake were reduced by three crops (sweet potato, cucumber, and rape). Furthermore, high porosity and surface area promote the nutrients and water retention capacity of biochar, which depicts its potential use in soilless cultivation. For example, Romina et al. [105] evaluated the performance of almond shell biochar for soilless cultivation of arugula (*Eruca sativa*) and found that characteristic of the arugula plant was improved by adding 10 % of biochar with water due to porosity, chemical composition, high re-wettability, and structural stability of biochar. However, the increased concentration of biochar (>10 %) showed an inhibitory effect on arugula plant growth. The adsorption capacity of conventional activated carbon is more than that of biochar, but biochar can be modified using various techniques to enhance its SA,

which makes it suitable for particular applications [106,107].

The CEC of biochar is considered an indicator to see the impact of biochar on soil fertility [47]. The high CEC of biochar indicates biochar has a significant capacity to adsorb positively charged nutrients (Mg⁺², Ca⁺², K⁺) on its surface to increase soil fertility [108]. Fig. 11c depicts that the CEC of PW biochar was highest, followed by CR, WB, and SHP in both temperature ranges. The high AC in CR and PW results in high CEC of biochar, which is due to alkali and alkali metals present in the AC, promoting the O-containing functional groups [101]. According to the data collected in this study, a significant effect of OT on the resulting CEC of biochar was not recorded. This was due to variation in measurement techniques of biochar CEC [109]. However, the literature presents that the CEC of biochar decreases with the increase in OT of pyrolysis due to the removal of O-containing surface functional groups (hydroxyl and carboxyl) [110]. The biochar that has high CEC (PW and CR biochar) depicts its potential for cationic and anionic nutrient retention and soil amendment [111].

The EC represents the soluble ion content present in biochar, which reflects the capability of the fertiliser [112]. Fig. 11d shows the EC of biochar from various feedstocks at different temperature ranges. Here, OT and feedstock type did not determine a significant difference in the mean values of EC observed between the feedstock's groups, likely due to the high degree of variability in the collected data. A high value of EC can affect the nutrient availability and soil salinity when used for agricultural applications [113]. Meanwhile, the lower EC can cause the rapid removal of fertiliser from the soil [112]. The EC of biochar varied with increasing the OT of pyrolysis due to a decrease in acidic functional groups and an increase in soluble salt content [114,115].

3.3.2.3. Nutrient contents. The results provide ample evidence that nutrient content is present in agro-industrial waste biochar, suggesting its agricultural applications as a fertiliser or soil amendment. The concentration of various nutrients in biochar obtained from various feedstocks at different temperature ranges is demonstrated in Fig. S11. The phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and calcium (Ca) were prominent in PW and WB biochar as compared to CR and SHP biochar in both temperature ranges. The P-rich biochar can be helpful for soil improvement that has a deficiency in P content. However, the concentration of P content in biochar from agro-industrial waste was relatively low compared to K, Ca, magnesium (Mg), and iron (Fe). However, the high K content in biochar needs attention because it can cause soil salinity. The moderate concentration of K in biochar can be effective in plant growth as it promotes root development [116]. The Mg and iron (Fe) were prominent in PW and WB biochar compared to SHP and CR biochar. The high Mg and Ca content biochar improves soil structure by buffering its acidity [117]. The manganese (Mn) concentration was the same and lower in all agro-industrial waste biochar. However, the high concentration of Mn and Fe in biochar can promote plant growth by enhancing soil microbial diversity [118]. The effect of pyrolysis OT on the concentration of nutrient content in biochar was unclear due to the diversity of feedstocks composition and low sample size in the defined temperature range.

3.3.3. Correlation analysis of biochar

The Pearson correlation analysis was performed between feedstocks properties, OT, and biochar properties. The correlation analysis on individual feedstock groups showed a complex pattern that was difficult to discuss consistently (Fig. S12). Therefore, to increase the significance of the discussion, the Pearson correlation analysis was performed on the whole biochar dataset, as shown in Fig. 12. Biochar obtained from high C-containing feedstocks yields more biochar, whereas biochar derived from high VM-containing feedstocks yields less biochar. Moreover, the results revealed that biochar yield and B_VM had a negative correlation coefficient with OT. Meanwhile, the B_ash, B_C, SA, and pH had a positive correlation coefficient with OT, as previously shown in Figs. 10 and

Fig. 12. Pearson correlation chart between feedstocks composition, biochar properties, and process parameters (whole dataset). OT: operating temperature, SA: surface area, CEC: cation exchange capacity, EC: electrical conductivity. In the heatmap, white colour represents the neutral correlation, dark red colour depicts the strong positive correlations, and dark blue colour shows strong negative correlations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

11. The correlation between EC and CEC with OT did not reflect the results presented in the literature due to the significant variations in the reported values. OT can control properties such as SA, pH, and B_VM during biochar production. Therefore, OT needs to be given preference when these biochar properties are essential for specific applications. Meanwhile, biochar's concentration of B_N, B_C, B_ash, nutrient contents, and CEC strongly depends on feedstocks properties, like C, N, and ash contents [119]. Thus, when biochar application requires these properties, preference should be given to the feedstock selection. However, some biochar properties, including B_C and B_ash, are obviously influenced by both OT and feedstock properties. For instance, higher ash and C content feedstocks produce higher B_ash and B_C, respectively, which rise with increasing OT, as shown in Fig. 12.

3.4. Bio-oil yield and energy potential

Bio-oil is a liquid product of pyrolysis obtained after the condensation of pyrolysis gas. Typically, the yield of bio-oil is calculated from Eq. (11).

$$\text{Oil yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Mass of oil (wt)}}{\text{Mass of feedstock (wt)}} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

Bio-oil composition is very complex as it contains different organic compounds and water. Bio-oil usually contains a significant amount of water content (15–35 %, sometimes even more) [120]. It also includes aldehydes, ketones, alcohols, furans, acids, aromatics, sugars, esters, and nitrogen compounds [17]. A detailed statistical investigation of bio-oil properties was not included in the current scope of study. However, the overview of bio-oil production from agro-industrial waste is provided. Table 3 shows the yield of bio-oil from various agro-industrial feedstocks at different temperatures. The yield of bio-oil increases with temperature increase, usually up to 500–600 °C, then it starts to decrease as the temperature further increases [121,122]. The initial

Table 3

The yield of bio-oil and HHV from various agro-industrial feedstocks at different temperatures.

Feedstock	OT (°C)	Bio-oil yield (%)	HHV of bio-oil (MJ/kg)	Ref.
Olive tree pruning	325	43.1	20.43	[122]
	400	42.4	23.44	
	400	41.1	24.12	
Olive pomace	650	43.9	23.36	[121]
	500	26	22.9	
	600	33	23.6	
	700	27	23.49	
Olive pit	500	44	32.59	[131]
Peach pit	500	33	32.66	[131]
Rice Husk	500	39.61	28.71	[132]
Olive Pomace	325	42.1	21.81	[122]
	400	39.2	25.66	
	500	38.7	26.95	
Wheat Straw	650	35.1	26.83	[133]
	550	38	22.31	
	550	34	18.12	
Sugarcane bagasse	550	54	16.35	[133]

increase in bio-oil yield below 600 °C was due to primary reactions (devolatilisation). Whereas the decrease in yield of bio-oil at higher temperatures is due to secondary reactions (gasification and vapour cracking), which promote the yield of pyrolysis gas [121], as shown in Section 3.2.1. Moreover, the other process parameters, such as heating rate and vapour residence time, also influence the yield of bio-oil [123]. The higher heating rate and longer vapour residence time promote the pyrolysis gas yield due to secondary reactions, which decrease bio-oil yield [17,124]. Therefore, fast pyrolysis is usually ideal for high bio-oil production due to moderate heating rate (<500 °C/s), and short vapour residence time (0.5–10 s) [15]. Apart from process parameters, the feedstock composition type significantly influences bio-oil yield. The agro-industrial wastes that contain higher cellulose content can produce more yield of bio-oil [120,125]. Thus, WB can produce more bio-oil because it contains a high cellulose content (as shown in Fig. 4).

The presence of organic compounds in bio-oil suggests its potential as a source of renewable energy. Typically, the range of HHV of bio-oil is 14–19 MJ/kg, without any upgrading [126]. The HHV of bio-oil depend on the water and oxygen contents present in the bio-oil; the higher the water and oxygenated compound, the lower the HHV of bio-oil. The increase in pyrolysis OT (>600 °C) decreases the yield of bio-oil; however, it increases the HHV of bio-oil due to the cracking of oxygenated compounds and reduction in water content [122,127]. Therefore, the bio-oil obtained at higher temperatures has higher C and lower O content [128]. The characteristics of the feedstock also affect the HHV of bio-oil; for example, higher C and H content in agro-industrial waste feedstocks raises the HHV of bio-oil, but higher moisture and O content in the feedstock lowers the HHV of bio-oil [17,129]. Compared to heavy petroleum oil, bio-oil has poor properties such as high viscosity and acidity, making it unsuitable for engine fuel [126]. However, the upgrade techniques such as hydrodeoxygenation, catalytic cracking, esterification, emulsification, etc., can be used to increase bio-oil usability for energy applications [130].

4. Conclusions

This systematic review comprehensively evaluated agro-industrial waste for sustainable pyrolysis processes that can be used as an energy source or to produce biochar and bio-oil. Pyrolysis gas and bio-oil are mainly used as an energy source to generate heat and electricity. Biochar can be used in various applications such as soil amendment, wastewater treatment, carbon sequestration, etc. A detailed analysis was performed on the properties of agro-industrial waste, pyrolysis gas, and biochar. Additionally, an overview of bio-oil production from various agro-

industrial waste was provided to see its potential for energy applications. The feedstocks analysis showed that the properties of HHV of PW, SHP, and WB were more than 18 MJ/kg due to high cellulose and lignin content. At the same time, the CR had low HHV (<18 MJ/kg) due to high hemicellulose and AC, which limited its solo utilisation for pyrolysis compared to other feedstocks. The pyrolysis gas analysis shows that the OT significantly impacts the composition and HHV of pyrolysis gas. The higher OT (451–1000 °C) results in a higher concentration of combustible gases (CO, H₂, CH₄, and C_nH_m) and a lower concentration of CO₂. The mean HHV of pyrolysis gas in agro-industrial waste was 11–18 MJ/Nm³ at higher temperatures among all feedstock groups, showing its potential to produce energy. The regression equation was modelled to predict the HHV of feedstocks and pyrolysis gas for agro-industrial waste, which shows high prediction accuracy for HHV of feedstocks (R² > 0.90), while low prediction accuracy for HHV of pyrolysis gas (R² < 0.57). However, in future research, prediction accuracy can be improved by using advanced techniques such as machine learning and ANNs. The biochar analysis on agro-industrial waste showed that WB and SHP biochar had good properties for adsorption application due to high SA and less B_{ash}. However, the biochar produced from CR was not of good quality due to the high portion of B_{ash}. The pH value of biochar showed an alkaline nature for agro-industrial waste at higher temperatures, which can be used to treat acidic soil amendment. Moreover, the analysis indicates that PW and WB biochar contain essential nutrients (P, Ca, and Mg) that can be used in agricultural applications. The HHV of bio-oil was in the range of 14–19 MJ/kg, which depicts its potential as a renewable fuel for a furnace or boiler. However, a detailed analysis of the bio-oil is as crucial as the ones mentioned for pyrolysis gas and biochar to understand the effect of feedstock types on the properties of bio-oil and to decide its end-use applications. This systematic review provides valuable insights into the sustainable exploitation of agro-industrial waste to produce renewable energy and biochar while managing waste from a circular economy perspective. Moreover, the established dataset on the pyrolysis of diverse agro-industrial wastes can be used to develop a strategy for blending different feedstocks based on their availability season. Future studies can focus on lifecycle assessment and techno-economic analysis to evaluate whether the on-farm utilisation of agro-industrial waste through pyrolysis is technically feasible, environmentally sustainable, and economically viable.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hamad Gohar: Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Giovanni Beggio:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marco Schiavon:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Maria Cristina Lavagnolo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2025.108047>.

Data availability

Data is available in SM

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